

STUDYING THE MORPHOMETRIC INDICATORS OF THE PANCREAS IN LABORATORY ANIMALS WITH INDUCED HYPERTIRHOSIS.

Togaeva G.S.

Samarkand State Medical University, Uzbekistan

Oripov F.S.

Scientific supervisor: Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor

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Annotation. Thyroid dysfunction is polyetiological and may be associated with developmental anomalies, genetic pathology, T-suppressor deficiency, and inflammatory process in thyroid tissue. The study used 30 rats to study the effects of experimental thyrotoxicosis. The rats were divided into two groups - the group with intact animals and the group with experimental hyperthyroidism. Hyperthyroidism was modeled by administering L-thyroxine in various doses over 14 days. Comparative analysis of the morphometric indicators of pancreatic cells in control and experimental rats showed that despite the fact that the total cell volume, cytoplasm volume, and nuclear volume of pancreatic cells in hyperthyroid rats were lower than in the control group animals.

Keywords: endocrine system, thyroid gland, pancreas, experimental animals, hyperthyroidism.

Relevance. Currently, there is a steady increase in thyroid pathology, therefore, the development of experimental models is of great importance for studying the pathogenesis, clinical presentation, treatment, and prevention of these diseases, the selection of which requires consideration of adequacy, validity, bioethics, and sensitivity to various physiological, pharmacological, genetic, and other manipulations. The World Health Organization notes that with each passing year, thyroid diseases are detected more frequently, approximately in every tenth inhabitant of the planet [1, 3, 5]. Thyroid dysfunction is polyetiological and can be associated with developmental anomaly, genetic pathology, T-suppressor deficiency, inflammatory process in thyroid tissue, congenital defect of enzyme systems, drug therapy, strumogenic effect of microelement deficiency, and other causes [2]. Taking into account the fact that the incidence of thyroid disease has been increasing recently, researchers' interest is directed towards the formation (selection) of experimental models of endocrine diseases for the purpose of studying and analyzing the pharmacological properties of new compounds, as well as reliably identifying the peculiarities in the mechanism of action of already known drugs [4].

Work objective. Assess the results of a comparative analysis of the morphological and morphometric indicators of the pancreatic parenchyma resulting from experimental hyperthyroidism.

Materials and methods. The study used 30 rats to study the effects of experimental thyrotoxicosis. The rats were divided into two groups - the group with intact animals and the group with experimental hyperthyroidism. Hyperthyroidism was modeled by administering L-thyroxine in various doses over 14 days. The material taken from the experimental animals after decapitation under anesthesia was placed in a plastic container for fixation in a 10% solution of neutralized formalin. Formalin cuts were washed with running water, dehydrated in increasingly concentrated alcohols, and paraffin blocks were prepared. Histological sections 5-7 μm thick were made from paraffin blocks and examined by hematoxylin-eosin staining and Van Gieson staining. Morphometric measurements were carried out at the resolution of the microscope 10×10, 10×20, and 10×40. Statistical processing of morphometric indicators was carried out using the Student-Fisher criterion, using the standard error of the arithmetic mean M/m of the relative value and the significance coefficient of the t-difference. As a result of the research, certain results were obtained.

Research results. For the experiment, 30 rats of the same age with the same body weight were selected. Morphometric indicators were studied. By creating an experimental model of hyperthyroidism, the parameters of morphological and morphometric reactive changes in the interstitial tissue of the pancreas and pancreatic cells of rats were studied and compared.

Comparative morphometric indicators of pancreatic pancreatic cells in rats (in relative units)

Table No. 1

	Nuclear volume	Cytoplasm volume	Total volume	Oy/Os ratio
Control group	3.95±0.11	11.42±0.33	15.37±0.40	0.36±0.01
Experimental hyperthyroidism	3.02±0.32	7.44 ± 0.29	10.46 ± 0.34	0.43 ± 0.02

Conclusion: Comparative analysis of the morphometric indicators of pancreatic pancreatic cells in control and experimental rats showed that despite the fact that the total cell volume, cytoplasm volume, and nuclear volume of pancreatic cells in hyperthyroid rats were smaller than in the control group

animals, the nuclear-cytoplasmic ratio was significantly higher by 15%. This situation means that the proliferative reaction of these cells in response to experimental exposure increases, which in turn can affect the organ's functional state.

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